

PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT METHODS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND AFFECTING FACTORS TO HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. Nowadays, the effectiveness of personnel management is not sufficient, but at the same time, many enterprises are paying more attention to this fact. However, the interest of the company's managers in the personnel is increasing, and the employees working with them are not sufficiently well formed. Therefore, in the conditions of strong competition and instability in the market, personnel policy is considered the most appropriate task for all enterprises.

Key words: personnel, enterprise, manager, management, competition, personnel management, enterprise personnel.

The competitiveness of any enterprise directly depends on the employees working in it and the personnel management system in this organization. Therefore, the modern concept of enterprise management envisages separation of functional tasks related to personnel management.

The main tasks of the personnel management system are: providing the enterprise with qualified employees; providing the necessary conditions for effective use of the experience of the company's personnel; improvement of the wage payment system and incentive measures; management of internal actions and careers of enterprise personnel; to give the organization's personnel the opportunity to improve their skills, etc.

However, in most cases, at present, the heads of local organizations focus on production management, enterprise finance, and marketing. At the moment, the process of human resources management remains the weakest link of the enterprise management system.

Organizational-administrative methods of personnel management are characterized by the need to strictly, coldly and immediately execute the decisions made by the leader, or the team tends to execute the leader's task only according to orders and instructions. Personal management is based on personal relationships, discipline and responsibility. Organizational-administrative influence is a direct administrative instruction in the mandatory description of management aimed at the object and persons being managed. In other words, the leader can give instructions that must be carried out directly to the supervisors of the workshops subordinated to him, and the supervisors to the foremen of the production sections in this workshop. Issuing orders and instructions that must be carried out by lower-level managers, monitoring their implementation, developing norms, correctly selecting and placing employees, transferring workers from one place to another, Rewarding or punishing is the responsibility of top leaders.

Figure 1. The main tasks of the personnel management system.

In personnel management, economic incentive methods are used when material and monetary incentives are more effective than other ways to perform work with leaders and achieve desired results. In the conditions of market relations, this method is given great importance. This method should be used in personnel management in such a way that the level of satisfying the material interests of each employee and team should be determined by their contribution to achieving the overall final results. This method is widely developed mainly in the USA and European countries.

Ethical and spiritual methods of personnel management will have high results if they are in addition to administrative-organizational and economic stimulation methods, as well as at the same time warmly welcomed by the team. This requires the formation of relationships based on mutual trust and mutual understanding between managers and personnel. This method is based on the large-scale participation of employees in the management of production, and the main goal of using this method is to create a healthy social and psychological climate in communities.

This method is widely developed in Japanese practice. The essence of personnel management includes a methodological and systematic analysis of the personnel formation process. Redistribution of tasks and labor within a specific enterprise with the help of social, organizational, economic and legal relations of the object of work and management. For the full use of labor resources of every member of the society, for more efficient operation of the enterprise as a whole, it is necessary to create optimal conditions for all-round development of employees. The management process is carried out according to certain rules. An important

principle of management activity is functional specialization combined with universality. The principles of personnel management are the rules, important requirements that managers must follow in the process of managerial activity to ensure the achievement of their goals: the principle of unity of management; the principle of unity of management and collegiality; combination of centralization and decentralization; controlling the execution of decisions; recruitment, selection and placement of employees.

The main tasks of personnel management are:

- 1) increasing competitiveness;
- 2) ensuring social efficiency of the team;
- 3) increase labor efficiency and get maximum profit.

There are two main approaches to solving personnel problems in foreign experience. The first approach focuses on the fact that "Management of human resources" covers strategic aspects of solving this problem, including issues of social development. "Personnel management" refers to managing more personnel quickly. The second approach is based on the fact that "human resources management" is primarily focused on issues of state regulation of labor and employment relations, and "personnel management" is focused on labor relations at the enterprise level. The differences in terminology may be due to the nature and directions of activity. For example, the term "personnel" is often used by small firms (meaning less than 100 employees). Large organizations with more than 2,500 employees prevail among users of the term "Human resources".

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